

Marital Satisfaction among Wives with Unemployed Husbands as a Result of Pandemic Covid-19 Impact

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Abstract :- The COVID-19 pandemic has had a negative impact on the Indonesian economy. As a result, many employees have been laid off on a large scale. The family economy that was disrupted due to layoffs also had an impact on marital relations. This study aims to see a picture of marital satisfaction in wives with their husbands being laid off due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The method used in this research is descriptive quantitative. Sampling was carried out using the Snowball Sampling technique. The reliability test was carried out using Cronbach's alpha technique. The subjects in this study were 100 wives who did not work with their husbands being laid off. The results of the empirical mean calculation in this study show that marital satisfaction between wives and husbands who have been laid off due to the COVID-19 pandemic is in a low category. Marital satisfaction in this study includes aspects of conflict management, joint decision making, and aspects of communication quality, which are in the low category, while aspects of trust, respect, empathy, and equality are in the very low category. Then the aspects of sexual and psychological intimacy are in the medium category.

Keywords:- Marital satisfaction, Covid-19 pandemic, wives with unemployed.

I. INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 entered Indonesia in early 2020 and spread very quickly. This has forced Indonesia to implement a lockdown and large-scale social restrictions (PSBB) in several areas in order to prevent the transmission of the COVID-19 virus in Indonesia. However, this large-scale social restriction has had a fairly broad impact, starting from the political, cultural, defense, and security aspects, public welfare, and the economy (Hasrul, 2020). The impact of the economic aspect also affects employment in Indonesia (Chairani, 2020). Economic conditions in Indonesia during the COVID-19 pandemic experienced losses nationally. Large-scale social restrictions have caused several business sectors to be unable to operate so that economic turnover cannot occur (Hadiwardoyo, 2020). One form of real impact on the economic sector during the COVID-19 pandemic is the occurrence of large-scale layoffs. Many employees are laid off, and the company is threatened with bankruptcy (Yamali & Putri, 2020). A total of 114,340 companies have laid-off and laid-off workers, with a total of 3.5 million affected workers, 1.1 million laid-off formal workers, and 380,000 laid-off workers. In addition, workers in the informal sector affected reached 630,000 people (Kemnaker, 2020).

The reduction of workers on a large scale certainly has an impact on the economy in the family sphere. Husbands who lose their jobs due to the termination of their relationship cause the emergence of limited income, which will have an impact on reducing the fulfillment of needs in the family. Economically, family planning becomes messy (Gunawan & Sugiyanto, 2011). Based on research conducted by Afni and Indrijati (2011) explains that material aspects that are not achieved affect marital satisfaction. In other words, an adequate economy supports the achievement of marital satisfaction (Srisusianti & Zulkaida, 2013). Meanwhile, Wismanto (2004) says that there is no marital satisfaction in couples who can be free from divorce.

Divorce in Indonesia has increased during the COVID-19 pandemic. Referring to data from the Central Statistics Agency in 2019, the divorce rate in Indonesia increased by 9% from the previous year. Meanwhile, according to data from the Ministry of Religion, as of August 2020, the divorce rate in Indonesia reached 306,688 cases. Meanwhile, according to data from the Soreang Religious Court, Bandung Regency, there was an increase in filing lawsuits. In June 2020 alone, there were 1,012 divorce lawsuits, where the average divorce filing was only around 700 to 800 cases per month. In addition, based on data from the Bekasi area religious court, since March 2020, there have been 3,111 divorce lawsuits. This figure is quite high when compared to 2019 data which reached 4,343. There are 1,714 cases of divorce lawsuits filed by women, while 640 cases of male divorce are still in the trial process. (Azma, 2020).

The factors that cause divorce are economic factors, responsibility, interference from third parties, and harmony. In addition, research conducted by Gordon (2020) says that another reason for divorce is stress and anxiety in individuals during the COVID-19 pandemic. Termination of employment causes the family economy to no longer experience income, thereby triggering pressure that causes excessive emotions in the husband as the breadwinner, which can lead to physical violence (Radhitya, Nurwati & Irfan, 2020). In addition to reducing marital satisfaction, layoffs also have an impact on domestic violence. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the economy is a major factor causing domestic violence. Based on data from the Indonesian Women's Association for Justice Legal Aid Institute (LBH APIK) shows that there were 110 cases of domestic violence during the COVID-19 pandemic that were reported within a period of 3 months. Based on the data presented by LBH APIK (Sabarini, 2020) Says that layoffs can lead to domestic violence that triggers divorce because there is no marital satisfaction between husband and

wife. Olson (2014) says that reciprocity that occurs between husband and wife becomes a strength in a long-term relationship. Dissatisfaction in marriage is one of the causes of husband and wife choosing the path of divorce. Srisusanti and Zulkaida (2013) argue that marital satisfaction is an important thing in a marriage where it is influenced by present and past factors. Meanwhile, Ardhianita and Andayani (2013) said that marital satisfaction is an important factor in the success of a marriage. Failure in a marriage occurs when one or more family members feel dissatisfied. Barriers to meeting the needs of one or more family members will cause dissatisfaction.

Marital satisfaction is a subjective evaluation between a husband and wife on their marriage based on feelings of satisfaction and happiness and pleasant experiences that occur in the married life of Fower and Olson (in Olson, Defrain & Schogrand, 2014). Husbands and wives who have a high level of marital satisfaction will display the characteristics of a happy marriage (Wisnuwardhani & Mashoedi, 2012). The importance of marital satisfaction in the household is because from the household, a family will be born, and there is a pattern of basic education that determines the quality of the family for the next generation (Julianto & Cahyani, 2017). In addition, increasing stability in marital satisfaction is also beneficial for psychological health and physical health, improves mood, and has good problem solving so as to reduce the risk of divorce and children still have a prosperous life. (Stutzer & Frey, 2006).

Research conducted by Reizer, Koslowsky, and Geffen (2020), shows that fear of the COVID-19 virus is negatively associated with marital satisfaction in wives. Supported by research conducted by Mansurali and Harish (2020), the results from this Indian subject show that marital satisfaction in couples in the red zone tends to be lower than in couples in the green or orange zone. The previous explanation showed the wife's lack of marital satisfaction during the COVID-19 pandemic. Based on the description above shows the importance of marital satisfaction in the household. In addition to minimizing the occurrence of divorce, it also increases the quality of life of married couples.

Based on the description above, the researcher is interested in research related to how to describe descriptively the marital satisfaction of the wife with the

condition of the husband being laid off during the COVID-19 pandemic.

II. METHODS

A. Sampel

The population and sample in this study were married women. The sample used was a wife whose husband was laid off due to the impact of COVID-19, and the wife lived at home with her husband. This study used 100 respondents. The sampling technique in this study is the snowball sampling method.

B. Measuring Intrument

This study uses a descriptive quantitative method with snowball sampling as a sampling technique. To measure the marital satisfaction variable, using the marital satisfaction scale proposed by Mackey and O'Brien (1995) with five alternative answers from very suitable to very inappropriate.

C. Data analysis Technique

The data analysis technique used was descriptive statistical analysis which was carried out using the SPSS version 22 application.

III. RESULTS

Referring to the data analysis that has been carried out, the validity of the measuring instrument in this study uses content validity which is carried out by the research lecturer as expert judgment. Content validity is systematization validity through testing the feasibility or relevance of the test content through rational analysis by a competent panel or through expert judgment (Azwar, 2012).

On the marital satisfaction scale, the item discrimination power test uses the Corrected Item Total Correlation item, which a score of 0.30 means it has a satisfactory distinguishing power. There are 31 items about marital satisfaction. Of 31 items, there are 22 items that meet the assessment requirements, while the other nine items do not meet the assessment requirements because the total score does not reach 0.30. Correlation items total 22 items. Reliability was tested using Cronbach's alpha. Referring to the results of the reliability test, the marital satisfaction scale in this study has a coefficient value of 0.907, so it can be said to be reliable.

Measuring Instrument	Empirical Mean	Hipotetical Mean	Category
Marital Satisfaction Scale Mackey & O'Brien (1995)	49,2	66	Low

Table 1: Marital Satisfaction Scale Results

The results of the descriptive analysis in this study are described by comparing the hypothetical mean with the empirical mean. The results of the analysis show that the empirical mean score of the marital satisfaction scale is

49.2, with a total of 22 items. It was concluded that marital satisfaction between wives and husbands who were laid off due to the COVID-19 pandemic was in a low category.

Dimension of Marital Satisfaction	Empirical Mean	Hipotetical Mean	Category
Containment Conflict	10,8	15	Low
Mutuality in decision making	11,0	15	Low
Quality of Communication	13,0	18	Low
rational values of trust, respect, empathic understanding and equity	2,95	6	Very Low
sexual and psychological intimacy	11,2	12	Medium

Table 2: Dimension of Marital Satisfaction Scale Results

While the categorization of each aspect of marital satisfaction, the aspect of containment of conflict shows the results of the calculation of the hypothetical mean of 15 having a higher score than the empirical mean of 10.8. So it can be concluded that the containment of conflict aspect is in a low category. The second aspect, namely mutuality in decision making, shows that the hypothetical mean of 15 has a higher score than the empirical mean of 11.06, so it can be concluded that the aspect of mutuality in decision making is in a low category. The third aspect, namely the quality of communication, shows that the result of the hypothetical mean of 18 has a higher score than the empirical mean of 13.08, so it can be concluded that the aspect of quality of communication is in a low category. The fourth aspect of rational values of trust, respect, empathic understanding, and equity shows that the hypothetical mean of 6 has a higher score than the empirical mean of 2.95, so it can be concluded that the aspect of rational values of trust, respect, empathic understanding, and equity is in the very low category. The fifth aspect, namely sexual and psychological intimacy, shows that the hypothetical mean of 12 has a higher score than the empirical mean of 11.2, so it can be concluded that the aspect of sexual and psychological intimacy is in the moderate category.

While the results are based on subject demographic data, including the age of marriage, age of the respondent, number of children, ethnicity of origin, husband's income before being affected by COVID-19, type of work of husband before being affected by COVID-19, the results of demographic data based on the age of marriage 2-5 years with the age of the subject more than 30 years have low marital satisfaction. In contrast to the age of marriage of 5-10 years, the level of marital satisfaction is higher. Subjects aged in the range of 21 to more than 50 years of marital satisfaction were in a low category. The results also show that subjects who do not have children have marital satisfaction in the very low category. Description of the subject based on ethnicity or region of origin, it appears that the subject as a whole comes from Betawi, Bugis, Sundanese, Java, Maluku, and Indramayu. The empirical mean score shows marital satisfaction is in a low category. based on the empirical mean score, the lowest marital satisfaction comes from the Betawi ethnic group

IV. DISCUSSION

This study was conducted with the aim of providing a description of marital satisfaction for wives with their husbands being laid off due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The empirical mean calculation shows that the wife's marital satisfaction is in a low category. Based on these results, it can be assumed that the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic condition resulted in large-scale layoffs that had an impact on the family sphere so that the family finances were disrupted. Based on the theory, this is because the condition of the husband experiencing termination of employment causes stress to married couples related to the economy, which has an impact on decreasing the quality of marital satisfaction. According to Srisusanti & Zulkaida (2013), wives who do not work and only rely on one source of income, namely husbands, feel that the income is not sufficient for the family's needs. In addition, according to Gordon (2020), the existence of stress and anxiety during the COVID-19 pandemic related to finances and health causes marital satisfaction to be low and leads to divorce.

Of the five aspects used, aspects of control conflict, aspects of mutuality in decision making, and quality of communication show that the empirical means are in a low category. Meanwhile, the aspect of Rational values of trust, respect, empathic understanding, and equity shows that the empirical mean is in the very low category. In addition, the aspects of Sexual and psychological intimacy show that the empirical mean is in the medium category. The above aspects show that the subject is less able to manage conflict well, lacks cooperation, has poor communication quality, mutual respect, intimacy, and poor quality of sexual relations. According to Utami (2018), Not all couples can achieve satisfaction in marriage. Based on the theory of marital satisfaction, according to Craig (2009) is an evaluation carried out between husband and wife related to married life that changes throughout the marriage itself.

Marital satisfaction is the strongest predictor of a household's survival or not. Marital satisfaction can also be seen from the extent to which the needs, hopes, and desires of husband and wife in undergoing their marriage are in the form of agreements, roles, role rules as husband and wife, and each other's rules as oneself (Zahra & Caninsty, 2016). The wife's dissatisfaction in marriage results in a negative impact on married life. One of the most severe impacts is the occurrence of divorce (Larasati, 2012). High divorce rates were found during the COVID-19 Pandemic. Divorce shows the lack of marital satisfaction between husband and wife. Couples who can no longer satisfy each other, serve, and find ways to solve problems that satisfy both parties will

lead to dissatisfaction in marriage. If it continues to be felt, husband and wife will experience divorce (Hurlock, 1994).

Descriptive analysis of research subjects based on aspects of containment conflict with the empirical mean is in a low category. Indicated by the attitude of the subject and partner, who are often involved in quarrels, the subject also does not understand. It takes issue with the condition of his husband, who is not having a job, creating conflicts in the household. When fighting, the wife does not forgive her husband and does not follow the husband's opinion, thereby reducing the quality of satisfaction in marriage. According to the purpose of marriage, everyone who gets married expects prosperity and satisfaction, but every marriage bond is often colored by conflict (Handayani & Harsanti, 2017). So it takes the ability to manage conflict in the household.

Descriptive analysis of research subjects based on the aspect of mutuality in decision making with the empirical mean score in the low category. Shown by the attitude of husband and wife who do not discuss economic problems with each other besides that the husband does not play much of a role in household matters such as raising children in online learning, the wife also does not want to help her husband in the economy and also decisions in purchasing goods in a household is often not discussed with the husband. Where of course, this can cause satisfaction in marriage to be lower.

The quality of communication with the empirical mean is in a low category. Indicated by the attitude of the subject and the partner who does not talk to each other, for example, about their respective likes or hobbies, which make the relationship more intimate, the two partners are not communicative about what is being felt, especially the wife, so they are often dishonest with each other. According to Ayub (2011), communication is one of the critical factors in creating marital satisfaction. Communication aims to understand each other regarding social life and ways of thinking. Therefore, communication plays an essential role in marital relations, which can trigger the development of a relationship and the achievement of satisfaction in marriage. Good communication is effective communication with openness, empathy, mutual support, a positive attitude, and equality (Devito, 1997).

Analysis of the description of the research subject based on aspects of rational values of trust, respect, empathic understanding, and equality with the empirical mean score at the very low-level category. Her attitude of not appreciating, respecting, and not treating her husband well when not working. Walgito (2000) said that mutual trust is one-factor affecting marital satisfaction. If one doubts his partner, he will appear insecure and hurt. Causes the marriage that is built to be threatened (Genova & Rice, 2008).

The results of the descriptive analysis of the research subjects were based on Psychological and sexual intimacy aspects, with the empirical mean score at the level of the medium category. This is indicated by the attitude of the subject and husband, who does not have much sexual intercourse and does not show too much romantic attitude

toward each other. The interaction of husband and wife also influences marital satisfaction. One of the processes of interaction in marriage is intimacy.

While the results are based on subject demographic data, including the age of marriage, age of respondents, number of children, ethnicity of origin, husband's income before being affected by COVID-19, type of work of husband before being affected by COVID-19, the results of demographic data based on the age of marriage 2-5 years with the age of the subject more than 30 years have low marital satisfaction. In contrast to the age of marriage of 5-10 years, the level of marital satisfaction is higher. Subjects aged 21 to more than 50 years of marital satisfaction are in a low category.

The results also show that subjects who do not have children have marital satisfaction in the very low category. Subject descriptions based on ethnicity or region of origin. The subjects are from Betawi, Bugis, Sundanese, Java, Maluku, and Indramayu. The empirical mean score shows marital satisfaction. They are in a low category. based on the empirical mean score, the lowest marital satisfaction comes from the Betawi ethnic group

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the empirical mean in this study shows that marital satisfaction is in a low category. In addition, aspects of marital satisfaction containing containment conflict, mutuality in decision making, and quality of communication show empirical scores, which are in the low category. Meanwhile, other aspects, namely, rational values of trust, respect, empathic understanding, and equity, show that the empirical mean is very low. Meanwhile, the sexual and psychological intimacy aspects of the empirical mean are in the medium category. In addition, the results of the analysis of research subjects based on marriage age 2-5 years with subject age 21-30 years, have 1-3 children, as well as those who come from Maluku, and earn 3-7 million / month and husband works as a marital security satisfaction is in a low category.

VI. SUGGESTION

It is hoped that husband and wife couples can pay attention to communication so that good conflict handling can be established. Besides that, wives better understand the condition of their husbands when they are in difficult times. Therefore, increase trust with the husband, understand each other, and give attention to good intimacy. In addition, the wife must manage family finances well in difficult financial conditions. As well as involve the husband in various household matters, such as educating children and distributing household chores. Also, pay attention to sexual relations to achieve marriage satisfaction.

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